

OVERSEAS EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE LIFE INSURANCE INDUSTRY

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Currently, many insurance products that are popular among the population in economically developed countries are now entering the national insurance market of our country. In this regard, the spread of life insurance in developed countries and the high level of its social significance indicate that its prospects are bright and its potential is high in our country.

In developed countries, the life insurance sector is an integral part of the financial infrastructure. Based on the activities of insurance organizations operating in foreign countries and their solvency, we can say that the level of development in different countries is different. The experience of many foreign countries has shown that the main part of collected insurance premiums is made up of insurance premiums from insurance types in the field of life insurance. In addition, it is life insurance that is the source of income and placement of free funds of the population in the most effective investment objects.

In 2018-2022, the share of life insurance in the insurance business was formed differently in different countries (Table 1).

Table 1

The share of the life insurance industry in the insurance business in some countries (relative to the volume of life insurance premiums)¹, in percent

r/p	States	Share of the life insurance industry in the insurance business				
		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	USA	41,3	39,7	40,4	25,5	25,0
2	China XR	56,3	58,7	54,5	53,4	53,0
3	Japan	75,1	72,8	75,9	74,3	71,0
4	Great Britain	65,5	67,0	70,0	72,1	70,6
5	France	64,3	63,5	64,0	63,9	59,1
6	Italy	75,4	73,3	73,6	74,0	73,2
7	Germany	44,0	43,5	39,9	41,6	41,2
8	South Korea	61,0	56,7	54,8	54,1	54,8
9	Taiwan	83,3	83,9	83,7	82,7	80,5
10	India	77,9	74,7	73,9	74,9	75,2
11	Hong Kong	92,0	81,3	92,6	92,5	92,2
12	Canada	43,6	43,2	42,3	40,0	40,6
13	Ireland	86,4	86,8	86,7	90,4	87,2
14	JAR	80,8	80,1	79,7	80,1	81,8
15	Brazil	56,4	56,3	53,9	55,7	55,8

¹ www.swissre.com

According to the annual report "World insurance" of Swiss Re Institute, in 12 of the 15 countries with the most developed life insurance sector, the share of life insurance sector in the country's insurance business is higher than 50 percent, which shows the importance of this indicator. Also, in countries where life insurance has developed dramatically in recent years (Hong Kong - 92.2 percent, Ireland - 87.2 percent, South Africa - 81.8 percent, Taiwan - 80.5 percent and India - 75.2 percent) from 75 percent it can be observed that it is high.

Based on the conducted studies, the share of insurance premiums in GDP was determined as an indicator of the level of development of the life insurance sector and compared between some countries of the world.

Table 2

Share of life insurance premiums in GDP ², in percent

r/p	Countries	Years				
		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	USA	2,82	2,88	2,9	3,07	2,6
2	Japan	6,26	6,72	6,67	6,69	6,1
3	Russia	0,36	0,47	0,47	0,37	0,4
4	China	2,68	2,3	2,3	2,3	2,1
5	Uzbekistan	0,047	0,10	0,12	0,065	0,10

According to Table 2, the share of insurance services in the GDP of the analyzed countries has grown in recent years. In particular, in 2021, compared to 2018, the share of insurance services in the US GDP increased by 0.25 percentage points and amounted to 3.07 percent. In Japan, this indicator increased by 0.43 percentage points and amounted to 6.69 percent. Although this indicator in Russia is not as high as in developed countries, there was an increase in 2019-2020. This indicator in Uzbekistan is significantly lower than the mentioned countries, but it does not have a high growth rate. The conducted analysis showed that cooperation between insurance companies and commercial banks in Russia is established at a high level, that is, on average 70% of life insurance products are sold through digital systems, which ensured an increase in the volume of insurance services.

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² www.swissre.com

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